

Review of Indira Awas Yojana - Housing Scheme of Government of India

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Abstract

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) was a housing scheme launched by the Government of India in 1985, aimed at providing housing to the rural poor. The scheme was renamed as Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin (PMAY-G) in 2016. This paper reviews the implementation and impact of the IAY scheme, including its design, funding, and execution. The paper analyzes the key achievements and challenges faced by the scheme, highlighting its contribution to improving the living conditions of the rural poor. The paper also suggests ways to enhance the effectiveness of the scheme to better serve the housing needs of the rural poor in India.

Keywords

Indira Awas Yojana, Housing Scheme, Awas Yojana, Housing Policy

Introduction

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) was a housing scheme launched by the Government of India in 1985, with the objective of providing housing to the rural poor. The scheme was implemented by the Ministry of Rural Development and aimed to assist households living below the poverty line to construct new houses or upgrade their existing ones. The scheme was later renamed as Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin (PMAY-G) in 2016. IAY/PMAY-G has been one of the flagship programs of the Indian government's poverty alleviation strategy, aimed at improving the living conditions of the rural poor by providing them with safe, secure, and hygienic housing. The scheme has been successful in providing affordable housing to millions of rural households across India, helping them to lead a life of dignity and security. This paper provides a review of the implementation and impact of the Indira Awas Yojana, analyzing its achievements, challenges, and future prospects.

Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin (PMAY-G) is a housing scheme launched by the Government of India in 2016, with the aim of providing affordable housing to the rural poor. It is a continuation of the earlier Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) scheme, with a renewed focus on providing

housing for all. Under the scheme, eligible beneficiaries receive financial assistance from the government to construct a pucca house, which includes a minimum of one room, a kitchen, and a toilet. The scheme also provides assistance for the renovation and up-gradation of existing houses. PMAY-G has been designed to ensure transparency, accountability, and timely completion of the construction of houses. The scheme is implemented by the Ministry of Rural Development and has been successful in providing affordable housing to millions of rural households across India. PMAY-G is one of the key initiatives of the Indian government's poverty alleviation strategy and has significantly contributed to improving the living conditions of the rural poor.

Findings and Discussion

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) was a housing scheme launched by the Government of India in 1985 with the aim of providing affordable housing to the rural poor. While the scheme was successful in providing housing to many rural households, there were some critical issues with its implementation.

Firstly, the eligibility criteria for the scheme were ambiguous, leading to exclusion of many deserving households. The definition of a "below poverty line" household was not clear, resulting in the exclusion of many deserving households from the scheme.

Secondly, the fund allocation for the scheme was often inadequate, leading to delays in the construction of houses. The funds were released in a phased manner, leading to a delay in the completion of the construction of houses.

Thirdly, the quality of construction was often poor, with many houses not meeting the basic standards of safety and durability. The use of sub-standard materials and the lack of proper supervision during construction led to poor quality construction, resulting in the collapse of houses in some cases.

Lastly, the scheme did not address the issue of land ownership, which was a crucial factor in the success of the scheme. The lack of clear land titles led to disputes and conflicts, which hindered the construction of houses.

Overall, while the Indira Awas Yojana was successful in providing affordable housing to many rural households, there were critical issues with its implementation, which need to be addressed in the current Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin scheme.

- Achievements of Indira Awas Yojana
- Provided housing to over 33 million rural households
- Reduced homelessness and improved living conditions for rural households
- Increased access to basic amenities such as water supply and sanitation
- Generated employment opportunities through construction activities

- Encouraged rural entrepreneurship and economic development
- Promoted social inclusion and empowerment of women and marginalized communities
- Contributed to the overall development of rural areas
- Increased awareness and participation of rural households in government schemes
- Strengthened rural infrastructure and connectivity
- Promoted sustainable housing and construction practices
- Reduced the incidence of diseases related to poor housing and sanitation

SWOT analysis of Indira Awas Yojana:

Strengths:

- Provided affordable housing to over 33 million rural households, reducing homelessness and improving living conditions.
- Increased access to basic amenities such as water supply and sanitation, promoting health and hygiene.
- Generated employment opportunities through construction activities, promoting economic development.
- Promoted social inclusion and empowerment of women and marginalized communities.
- Contributed to the overall development of rural areas, strengthening infrastructure and connectivity.

Weaknesses:

- Ambiguous eligibility criteria, leading to the exclusion of deserving households.
- Inadequate fund allocation, leading to delays in construction and poor quality construction.
- Lack of clear land titles, leading to disputes and conflicts over land ownership.
- Insufficient awareness and participation of rural households in the scheme.

Opportunities:

- The current government's Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin scheme offers an opportunity to address the weaknesses of Indira Awas Yojana and improve the implementation of the scheme.
- Advances in technology and innovation can be leveraged to improve the quality and sustainability of housing construction.

Threats:

- Natural disasters such as floods and earthquakes can damage housing infrastructure and hinder the implementation of the scheme.
- Inadequate provision for disaster-resilient housing can lead to the loss of life and property in case of natural disasters.
- Limited access to credit and finance can hinder the construction of houses for deserving households.

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) was a flagship scheme of the Government of India aimed at providing affordable housing to the rural poor. The scheme was launched in 1985 and has provided housing

to over 33 million rural households since its inception. However, despite its achievements, the scheme has faced several criticisms and challenges.

One of the major criticisms of the scheme is the ambiguous eligibility criteria, which has led to the exclusion of deserving households. This has resulted in many eligible households being left out of the scheme, while some ineligible households have managed to secure benefits.

Inadequate fund allocation has been another major challenge, leading to delays in construction and poor quality construction. This has resulted in many houses being unfit for habitation, or requiring extensive repairs soon after construction.

Lack of clear land titles has also been a major challenge, leading to disputes and conflicts over land ownership. This has resulted in many houses being constructed on disputed land, leading to legal complications and the displacement of households.

Insufficient awareness and participation of rural households in the scheme has also hindered the effective implementation of the scheme. Many eligible households are not aware of the benefits of the scheme or are unable to navigate the bureaucratic process of applying for benefits.

In conclusion, while Indira Awas Yojana has made significant contributions to reducing homelessness and improving living conditions in rural India, it has also faced several criticisms and challenges. Addressing these challenges and improving the implementation of the scheme will be crucial to ensure that the benefits of the scheme reach all eligible households and contribute to the overall development of rural India.

Conclusions

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) was a significant scheme launched by the Government of India in 1985 with the objective of providing affordable housing to the rural poor. The scheme has provided housing to over 33 million rural households, reducing homelessness and improving living conditions in rural India. It has also generated employment opportunities through construction activities and promoted social inclusion and empowerment of women and marginalized communities.

However, the scheme has also faced several criticisms and challenges, including ambiguous eligibility criteria, inadequate fund allocation, delays in construction, poor quality construction, lack of clear land titles, and insufficient awareness and participation of rural households.

Despite these challenges, Indira Awas Yojana has made a significant contribution to the overall development of rural India. The scheme has strengthened infrastructure and connectivity in rural areas, improved access to basic amenities, and contributed to the economic development of rural

areas. Moreover, the scheme has promoted social inclusion and empowerment, particularly for women and marginalized communities.

In conclusion, Indira Awas Yojana has been a crucial scheme in addressing the housing needs of the rural poor in India. While it has faced several challenges and criticisms, the scheme has made significant contributions to the overall development of rural India. The scheme highlights the importance of addressing the housing needs of the poor and marginalized communities and emphasizes the need for effective implementation and monitoring of such schemes.

References

- 1) Biswas, S. (2015). The Role of Indira Awaas Yojana in Addressing Rural Homelessness: An Evaluation. *Int J Humanities Social Sci Studies*, 2(2), 364-374.
- 2) Chakraborty, L., & Bandyopadhyay, K. (2017). Evaluation of Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY): A Study on Rural Housing in West Bengal. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 19(4), 1-10.
- 3) Dhar, S. (2018). Housing Policies in India: An Overview. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 7(2), 1225-1229.
- 4) Hazra, S. (2018). Housing for All: Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences*, 8(7), 423-427.
- 5) Hussain, M., & Yaseen, G. (2017). A study of loopholes in selection criteria of Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY) scheme in district Anantnag of Kashmir valley. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences (IJRESS)*, 7(6), 472-483.
- 6) Jana, S. (2018). An Analysis of Indira Awas Yojana in the Context of Rural Housing in India. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 198-204.
- 7) Jiyawan, R., & Mishra, O. P. (2013). Indira Awas Yojana-Hope of Roof over Rural Poor Head: A Critical Analysis. *Journal of Community Mobilization and Sustainable Development*, 8(1), 14-23.
- 8) Ministry of Rural Development. (2017). Indira Awaas Yojana: Guidelines for Construction of Houses. Government of India. Retrieved from http://mord.gov.in/downloads/IAY_Guidelines.pdf
- 9) Nigam, N., & Kala, P. (2017). India's Housing Shortage and Policy Responses. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 52(43), 17-19.
- 10) Patil, S. (2015). Reviewing the Indira Awas Yojana: the politics of an awas. *Context*, 11, 151.
- 11) Patnaik, U. (2018). Housing in Rural India: An Overview. *International Journal of Rural Management*, 14(1), 1-15.
- 12) Sahoo, S. (2017). Assessment of Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana (Gramin) in Odisha: A Study of Rural Housing. *International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature*, 5(1), 187-196..
- 13) Singh, R., & Singh, J. (2018). Housing for All by 2022: A Study of Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana in Haryana. *Journal of Economic & Social Development*, 14(2), 98-110.
- 14) Sudarshnam, G., & Kumar, M. A. (2005). Rural Housing for Weaker Sections—A Study of Indira Awas Yojana (IAY). *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, 51(3), 566-594.
- 15) Sujatha, K. S., & Ramesh, M. (2018). Performance of Indira Awaas Yojana in Rural Karnataka: An Evaluation. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119(12), 1505-1512.
- 16) Vimala, V., & Sarala, K. S. (2012). Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY): Performance and Evaluation in Coimbatore District. *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1, 173-185.

- 17) Yadav, S. K., & Gupta, R. (2017). Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana: A Step Towards Housing for All. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Management, Engineering and Technology*, 4(10), 139-143.
- 18) Yadav, S. K., & Singh, P. (2018). Indira Awaas Yojana: A Critical Evaluation of Rural Housing Programme in India. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research*, 5(11), 264-268.
- 19) Yadav, S., Singh, P., & Upadhyay, A. (2019). A Study on Indira Awaas Yojana: A Critical Analysis of Rural Housing Programme in India. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(6), 1338-1342.